

WHAT MOTIVATES US

DECIDO's three years objectives

Support Public Authorities in evidence-based policymaking

Ensure that data do contribute to policymaking

Actively involvement of local actors in data generation

Assess transformative impacts in disaster risk management applied in pilot sites

Pursue sustained use of data analytics in policymaking

OUR PARTNERS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation under grant agreement N° 101004605

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Decido

evidence and Cloud for more Informed and effective policies

THE CONTEXT

DECIDO consortium brings together innovative public administrations, leading European ICT service providers and research institutions to create new solutions to complex problems.

The opportunities that digital technologies offer are yet to be fully seized by Public Authorities. Complex problems such as migration, poverty, and climate change faced by today's society are increasing complexity for European governments as they do not have a single optimal solution. To cope with such challenges, data-driven policymaking aims to make use of data sources, analytical techniques and processing power to provide policymakers support in their decisions while involving local communities in co-creation activities to support better targeted policies.

DECIDO will use European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) as a contact point with the European Research Community. Seamless linking of open research data and public sector information will create optimal conditions for open innovation with high societal impact.

OUR GOAL

The overall aim of DECIDO is the creation of a bridge between Public Authorities and EOSC with a twofold objective: on the one hand to widen the use of the European Cloud Infrastructure services and data to Public Authorities, on the other to enable and encourage Public Authorities to use appropriate infrastructures, services, data and methodologies to apply a more evidenced informed approach to policies.

The result of the project will be the identification of a set of pathways, recommendations and a sound business plan directing Public Authorities through the transition towards the use of the European Cloud Infrastructure and the application of evidence and co-creation in the policy lifecycle.

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OUR MISSION

The mission of DECIDO is to demonstrate the groundbreaking impact of the adoption of innovative methodologies, tools and data enabling the effective development of better evidence-based policies by Public Authorities.

DECIDO will link Public Administrations to the data and compute infrastructure of the European Open Science Cloud – piloting the access to and exploitation of a great wealth of additional resources. The project will identify and assess the benefits and limitations in using current big data methodologies and infrastructures in policymaking in several domains.

